

Impact of Web Enabled Knowledge Platform: An Analysis

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Abstract: Knowledge portal in the study represents the knowledge organization. Many learners fail to acquire knowledge because of improper school facilities, faculties residing in remote areas, jobs or business tasks etc. Knowledge management represents a systematic means of acquiring, sharing and using knowledge effectively. This paper explores web-based systems to connect learners and faculties using knowledge management methodologies via a web-based portal. A systems analysis and design process was done to understand the needs of various stake holders of education system. Based on these explorations, knowledge portal was developed to fill a perceived gap in knowledge sharing and accessibility. Knowledge portal www.eknowledgecell.net was deployed with theme 'anytime anywhere' education. The key query was to identify the factors affecting the importance of knowledge portals and few other factors responsible for its wider acceptability. Empirical research was done and data was collected through participation of 537 learners. Through regression analysis it was found that the Factor 'Quality of the teachers and of their lectures' has the most influence followed by factor 'Learning Content', 'Knowledge Impact', 'Instant Communication' and 'Administration'.

Keyword: Web Portal, Knowledge Management, Education, Learner.

1. INTRODUCTION

Web portals can serve as powerful tools to help knowledge organizations improve their joint activities. They can facilitate knowledge achievement, sharing and discovery by allowing teachers and learners to publish documents, share ideas, work collaboratively and store information and knowledge in easily searchable repositories. Portals are becoming an increasingly important part of the information and communication technology infrastructure of organization as they seek to integrate the vast intellectual resources within a central virtual space that is easily accessible via a web interface.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Web Portals

A web portal or links page is a web site that functions as a point of access to information in the World Wide Web. A portal presents information from diverse sources in a unified way. An Internet portal is "a single integrated, ubiquitous, and useful access to information (data), applications, and people" (IBM, 2000). More than simply an archive of information, portals facilitate

a dynamic exchange of knowledge, data and information. By compiling content from multiple sources, they limit redundancy and competently increase the diffusion of information.

To improve productivity by increasing the speed and customizing the content of information provided to internal and external constituencies. Portals serve a knowledge portal function by "dealing with information excess in an organized fashion Daigle & Cuocco (2002).

Web portals have been used to simplify and systematize organizational functions in education. The most recent application of portals in education has been to create a theme of access for organizational tasks for students, such as registration, academic records, or for staff, such as schedule, financial information and the like (Olsen, 2002). In this way, use of portals maximizes efficient use of staff and students' time (Pickett, 2002).

By binding the ability of portals to create learning communities, portals can further influence the huge intellectual capital based contained within the organization via collaborative, synergistic activities.

Portals also serve to authorize entities within added broadly defined community. By providing easy accessibility to both clear and implied knowledge as

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well as groups of practice, individuals are not controlled by geographic or other physical barriers in terms of interactive and discovering new knowledge. “The portal will improve the efficiency of knowledge exchange and deliver a set of shared business objectives that include communications around best practices, a gateway to research on the use of teaching and learning through technology, professional development, policy development and review and resource development” (Kidwell, 2000). Portals facilitate knowledge transfer through the inclusion of multiple communication channels, such as memorandum boards and almanacs; moving beyond the one-sided information exchange found in traditional web sites.

2.2. Knowledge Portal

Using knowledge portal techniques and technologies in education is as vital as it is the corporate sector. If done effectively, it can lead to better decision-making capabilities, reduced “product” development cycle time improved academic and administrative services and reduced costs (Kidwell 2000). The same factors, such as competition for students and resources, which have led education institutions to implement knowledge portal systems in their administrative functions, make the case for expanding knowledge portal practices to teaching and research as well.

The creation of knowledge portal systems which tap into these existing pockets of knowledge is still in its infancy. Knowledge portal is a new field, and experiments are just beginning in education. We believe there is tremendous value to education institutions that develop initiatives to share knowledge to achieve business objectives (Kidwell 2000). Institutions face increasing competition for students and resources. One important factor in attracting students and obtaining resources is the caliber of an institutions’ faculty. The roles of teacher demand that staff pose as the expert, and that their security and credibility with students and colleagues is dependent upon their knowledge base (Rowley 2000). To excel in the future, education institutions have to manage explicitly, systematically and comprehensively from a knowledge perspective” (Steyn 2002).

Knowledge portal facilitates the transfer of existing knowledge and the creation of new knowledge, including interdisciplinary collaborations. Building publicly accessible repositories of scholarly expertise and interest, to promote transparency and information

exchange (Cronin 2001). Using knowledge portal to systematically create channels and opportunities for knowledge transfer will help preserve and disseminate tacit knowledge within the institution. Many faculty members possess institutional knowledge (Steyn 2002). It is a challenge to convert the information and skills currently residing in individuals and make them widely and easily accessible to all faculty members (Steyn 2002).

2.3.e knowledge Portal Overview

Knowledge portal web site www.eknowledgecell.net was developed with aim to impart ‘anytime anywhere’ education to learners.

This portal has features of registration login for teachers and students. Administrator manages the portal.

Other features include online communication

Other features of portal include profile management of faculties and learners, Quick Communication through Online contact and SMS. Facilitation of uploading and downloading of documents, audio and video files. Forum management of various groups on this different topic is conceptualized.

The portal is also designed to conduct surveys from various entities viz faculties, students and other stake holders.

3. SURVEY

3.1. Ideology, Philosophy, and Goals

The e knowledge portal reflects an underlying belief in the benefits of using technology in a self-study format. With this approach, learning is customized to the needs of the individual. The underlying theory is that portals ensures a high-quality pedagogy and is a superior training method because of its flexibility. The vision of education is a self-study technology-based model with frequent tests and a facilitating role for instructors. The core of the teaching philosophy is that

learner self-reliance is highly beneficial for learners. The portal is dedicated to global distance education and e-learning. The portal is supported by one-on-one tutoring via e-mail, chatting, online lectures, video based training, audio based training, online notes and assignments are uploaded and downloaded by ICT means.

3.2. Underlying Values

- Belief in technology
- Learner-centered philosophy
- Testing requirements
- Relevance
- “Hard” and “soft” skills
- Geographical reach
- Flexible access
- Respect for diversity

3.3. Objectives

The survey and interview findings showed that the portal design has many strengths and that the objectives were clear to the learners: 74% of participants felt that the learning objectives were explicit and clear all or most of the time, over 71% could find basic information in the portal all or most of the time; and 69% felt that the portal helped them understand what was expected from them. The individualized nature of the portal design is another major strength.

3.4. Study Materials

The study materials were orientation manual, computer training materials on the hard drive, and online resources. The knowledge portal is an enhanced self-study environment, with online study materials, CD-ROMs, and instructional videos.

4. KNOWLEDGE PORTAL FEATURES

4.1. Learner Satisfaction

The response of learners to the portal was very positive: 70% of portal participants felt that the organization and progression of the topics in this portal were sensible and coherent; 66% felt that the sequencing of topics was coherent and logical; 76% felt that the assignments were specified sufficiently for them to know what to do for the assignment; 77% felt that the way topics is taught is appropriate for the material; and 79% felt each

topic contained examples or activities that prompted them to use their own knowledge and experiences to understand the material.

4.2. Geographical Reach

The portal provides access to professional development for staff and supervisors in different regions as well as the flexibility they need to fit the portal into their schedule.

4.3. Record Keeping

A broad range of formats were used for the management of student records, including both the filing of student assignments, copies of e-mails sent and received, and monthly progress reports (MPRs). Interviews with tutors revealed that most student records are paperless. Some who began with extensive paper records later moved mostly to an electronic format.

4.4. Assessment

Ninety-five per cent of portal participants felt that the assessment tasks helped them to develop knowledge and skills identified in the learning objectives; 82% felt that each topic provided activities for testing or self-monitoring their own learning. The responses to the item about course workload show more variation than the responses to the previous survey items. Between 50% and 60% of portal participants felt that the workload was too great all or most of the time, whereas a minority (between 13% and 33%) felt it was too great very little or none of the time. All portal participants felt that (1) the tutor was interested in helping them to learn, (2) the feedback was helpful to their learning, and (3) the feedback on their work was provided promptly and normally not later than 2 weeks. Ninety-two per cent of portal participants felt that the tutor gave them individual help. All portal participants felt that marked work was returned promptly, 92% felt that comments on their marked work indicated things they had done correctly or well, and 91% felt that comments on their marked work indicated the sorts of things they could do to improve.

4.5. Quality Assurance: TMAs

The portal providers engaged subject experts to review (Tutor Marked Assignments) TMAs to ensure that the tutors' comments on students' papers meet their high standards. First, tutors send a copy of all marked

assignments for filing to the portal administrator. At least once, the portal administrator then selects two marked assignments at random and evaluates them for convergence with the ideal TMA. TMAs that are close to the model marked assignment receive school scores, while others receive lower scores. Of a maximum score of 10, average scores range from 6.65 to 7.1.

4.6. Relevance

Ninety-five per cent of portal participants felt that the content of each topic was deliberately related to the workplace; 96% of portal participants felt that the assigned written work improved their writing and analytical skills.

4.7. Negative Unintended Consequences

Course Noncompletion 23% of the respondents did not completed the course due to their own personal reasons.

Learner Nonresponse 13% learners stopped responding after few interactions.

4.8. Positive Unintended Consequences

4.8.1. Quality Assurance

There were several unexpected positive unintended consequences. First, the TMA review process functions as a professional development opportunity for tutors. Tutors are given samples of marked student assignments with tutor comments that represent the ideal in terms of tenor, locus, and relative emphasis and format (footnotes in the text, with comments underneath the student's work). All of the tutor felt that a quality assurance mechanism was a major strength of the portal.

4.8.2. Rejuvenating Effects of the Tutor

Finally, the monthly tutor discussion group provided not only regular professional development opportunity for tutors but also "a community."

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1. Research Questions

1. To identify factors influencing Knowledge Portal's impact?
2. To know the rank of influence of individual factors affecting "Knowledge Portal's impact"?

Validity of the portal was tested through a Knowledge questionnaire. The Knowledge survey was carried out. Responses were collected from 537 registered candidates. The questionnaire comprised 18 questions relating to elements that compose Knowledge Portal’s impact. The questionnaire was of the closed type. Respondents evaluated in questions 1 to 18 certain quality elements (shown in Table 1) of Knowledge Portal’s impact on a scale from 1 (very bad) to 10 (very good).

6. DATA ANALYSIS

For questions 1 to 16 (where a scale of answers from 1 to 10 was provided) Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was calculated. The value calculated is 0.914, which indicates great reliability of measurement. The sample consisted of 358 boys and 179 girls (N = 537).

3. Contents upload facility
4. Online communication with faculty and fellow students
5. Forum and topic wise discussion
6. Quick query response through SMS
7. The complete design of the knowledge portal
8. Connection to other faculties;
9. Usefulness of gained knowledge;
10. Quality of the teachers;
11. Faculty impact

The frequency tables for all of the variables that represent the elements that compose Knowledge Portal’s impact are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Frequency table for variables

	<i>N = 537</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
	<i>Valid</i>	<i>Missing</i>			
1	537	0	7.4830	8	1.67626
2	537	0	7.0896	7	2.02232
3	537	0	8.2754	9	1.89933
4	537	0	6.9091	7	1.84704
5	537	0	6.2551	7	2.05033
6	537	0	6.1954	7	2.04828
7	537	0	6.5183	7	2.08188
8	537	0	8.1194	8	1.68170
9	537	0	7.5455	8	1.90919
10	537	0	6.9959	7	1.97160
11	537	0	6.5115	7	1.94634
12	537	0	6.5482	7	1.92401
13	537	0	6.3935	7	1.94974
14	537	0	6.1954	7	2.23481
15	537	0	5.6784	6	2.31394
16	537	0	6.2985	7	2.07480
17	537	0	5.8318	6	2.08160
18	537	0	7.0461	7	2.20746

Table 2
Rotated Component Matrix (a, b)

	<i>Component</i>							
	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>
Learning through Audio files								.806
Learning through Video files								.707
Contents upload facility			.635					
Online chatting with faculty and fellow students					.700			
Forum and online group discussion					.816			
Quick query response through SMS					.716			
The complete design of the knowledge portal						.663		
The transfer of knowledge between teachers and learners						.701		
The study program’s actuality;						.668		
Connection to other faculties;	.683							
Usefulness of gained knowledge;	.714							
Quality of the teachers;	.802							
Faculty impact			.747					

All questions were referring to the elements that compose the impact of knowledge portal and all evaluations were given on a scale from 1 (very bad) to 10 (very good). The learners were asked to evaluate how they perceive:

1. Learning through Audio files
2. Learning through Video files

Again factor analysis was conducted. Following methods and parameters were used for the calculation:

- Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
- Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
- Suppression of small coefficients: Absolute value below: 0.7
- Selection variable: “Portal impact”, Value of the selection variable: 5.

On the basis of this factor analysis we obtained five new factors from 16 elements of impact and the selection variable as seen in Table 3.

Table 3
Coefficients (a)

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	7.671	0.044		171.826
Factor 1: “Instant Communication”	.306	.042	.171	7.549
Factor 2: “Learning content”	.363	.038	.227	9.290
Factor 3: “Administration”	.224	.041	.119	5.359
Factor 4: “Quality of the teachers and of their lectures”	.497	.034	.376	14.571
Factor 5: “Knowledge impact”	.350	.041	.195	8.405

The new variables (factors) are:

1. Factor 1: “Instant Communication”
2. Factor 2: “Learning content”
3. Factor 3: “Administration”
4. Factor 4: “Quality of the teachers and of their lectures”
5. Factor 5: “Knowledge impact”.

We have suppression the small coefficients with absolute values below 0.7. Regression analysis was conducted, from which it was found the influence of factors on the dependent variable (see Table 2 and Table 3). The dependent variable was the impact of the knowledge.

7. RESULTS

Factor 4: “Quality of the teachers and of their lectures” has the most influence ($\beta = 0.376$). It is followed by other factors which are listed by their importance: Factor 2 “Learning Content” ($\beta = 0.227$), Factor 5 “Knowledge Impact” ($\beta = 0.195$), Factor 1 “Instant Communication” ($\beta = 0.171$), Factor 3 “Administration” ($\beta = 0.119$). We have also found out that all five factors are important with statistical significance levels below .005. It is found that the five new variables can account for 56.5% of the variance of grades of the faculty.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations include better alignment of the portal and teaching materials and more remote access, the portal has since been redesigned with technology as the centerpiece of a true remote-access portal, with web-and video-based technologies.

8.1. Revise the Portal

Comments from tutors and learners show that Module works well for most learners, but some needed more clarification about the instructions and activities for Module.

8.2. Regular Reminders

The importance of regular and frequent contact with tutors was a recurring theme throughout the survey. One recommendation is to intimate progress with regular reminders.

9. CONCLUSION

Based on the knowledge of the theories and results of research, attempt is made to find factors responsible for putting a very high impact of a knowledge portal on the students as well as teachers both. Through the empirical research offered, actual importance of the learners is revealed that five factors mainly influence the knowledge portal’s significance, like “Quality of teachers and their lectures”, “Learning Content”, “Knowledge Impact”, “Instant Communication” and “Administration”. As present study is based on only two stakeholders – the learners and faculties, further research including other stakeholders, like the media, the alumni, experts etc. is desired.

The need for knowledge acquisition and knowledge sharing is readily acknowledged. Challenge was in the

translation of user requirements, gleaned from interviews, into a simple, easy-to-understand site organization that could easily navigate through the complexities of research areas. In meetings with the faculty and learners, the feeling is rebounded that a web-based knowledge system is greatly needed to facilitate collaboration and synergistic efforts across and within the different academic areas. While the learner and faculty interactions focused primarily on web site usability issues, most of the faculties did mention the advantage of having a virtual collaborative space available. This research represents a starting point in knowledge management implementation.

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